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- Poetry
- Short Stories
- Essays
- Spotlight on Emerging Writers
- Creative Corner
- Others

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Email: binasbookers2013@gmail.com

ERNESTO A. MIBULOS JR. MAEd

Teacher III

Villa Jacinta National Vocational High School

ernestojr.mibulos@deped.gov.ph

“THINK-PAIR-SHARE: A KINETIC STRATEGY TO PROMOTE SOCIAL STUDIES LEARNING”

Many students see Social Studies as a boring subject, often associating it with memorizing dates, names, and facts that feel far removed from their lives. This perception can make it difficult for them to appreciate the relevance and importance of the lessons. That is why teachers must find creative ways to bring the subject to life-by connecting topics to real world issues, using interactive activities, and presenting history and culture as living stories rather than static information. With the right approach, what once felt dull can become an engaging journey that sparks curiosity and a deeper understanding.

As an educator for more than a decade, both in private and public institutions, including my teaching experience in HEI or Higher Education Institution, I found out that this strategy is effective in teaching Social Studies classes. Think-Pair-Share (TPS) on the other hand, is a cooperative learning strategy where students first individually consider a question or problem, then discuss their ideas with a partner, and finally share their thoughts with the larger group. This learning strategy was successfully developed by Frank Lyman at the University of Maryland in 1981. With the utilization of this strategy, it is expected that students get time to think critically, creating a learning environment that encourages high-quality responses (**Rowe, 1972**).

For instance, in teaching world history: **(Think)**, students analyze a primary source like a letter from an American soldier to his wife during the Japanese invasion in the Philippines. **(Pair)** students will now discuss their interpretations with a partner, comparing their notes and challenging each other's assumptions. **(Share)** groups present their crafted interpretations and findings to the entire class, leading to a broader and wider discussion on the topic. By tactically integrating TPS with primary sources, educators can create a dynamic and engaging learning environment where students actively participate in the construction of historical knowledge. Thus, it promotes democratic education through fostering active-student participation, collaboration, and equitable access to learning opportunities. It also encourages students to engage with the material given, and develop their ideas through discussion.

Moreover, Think-Pair-Share (TPS) can be efficaciously be integrated into Geography lessons to make learning more piquant by prompting them to individually reflect on a geographical concept and data. For example in the discussion of Latin America- Geography and Culture **(Think)** recall what know about its countries, land forms, climate, and cultural influences.

(Pair) students pair up with a classmate to discuss their ideas. They compare answers, add new information they might have missed, and note at least three key features of Latin America's geography (e.g., Amazon Rainforest, Andes Mountains, major rivers and climate zones). **(Share)** their general insights with the whole class, the teacher lists their points on the board, grouping them under themes such as physical geography, climate, and cultural diversity. Thus, this collective sharing reinforces understanding and promotes collaboration and teamwork among students. For over a decade of using this strategy in my class, I have consistently seen how it transform student participation and deepens understanding, it creates a safe space for learners to process their thoughts, share ideas with peers, and feel confidently express themselves to the larger group.

Conclusively, this strategy not only improves comprehension but also addresses the 21st-century skills in education such as critical thinking, creativity, communication, collaboration and flexibility, this strategy perhaps be used across disciplines. Based on these proven classroom results, I can confidently say that Think-Pair-Share is an effective and highly commendably strategy in teaching Social Studies.

